

ratio were higher with maize alone, followed by maize at 2.5-m row spacing.

Rice - maize intercropping may be more profitable than rice alone. Further research is needed to select appropriate rice varieties and fertilizer management for the system. □

Performance of oilseed and pulse crops in a rice-based cropping sequence

G. Singh and O. P. Singh, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Crop Research Station, Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

Long-duration rice varieties and excess moisture delay sowing of dry season crops in the rainfed lowlands. Oilseeds and pulses are cultivated as relay or sequence crops, but yields are poor because of poor plant stands due to lack of adequate nutrients.

We studied the effect of seed rate and fertilizer on the productivity of a rice-based cropping system 1986-87 to 1988-89, in a randomized block design with four replications.

Economic analysis

Use of bullock power in rice production

T. R. Shanmugam, Veterinary College and Research Institute, Namakkal 637002, Tamil Nadu, India

Draft animal power is a critical component of rice-based cropping systems in Tamil Nadu. Rice requires more animal power than other crops because transplanting involves extensive tillage: plowing, puddling, bunding, and leveling. We studied the cost of draft animal power use on rice farms using 1971-72 to 1983-84 data from the scheme on Cost of Cultivation of Principal Crops (CCPC) covering the state's rice belt.

Bullock pair hours/ha fluctuate. Bullock costs/ha have increased (see table). But the proportion of total

Yields and net return^a of rice-based cropping systems in rainfed lowlands. Ghagharaghat, UP, India, 1986-89.^b

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)		Cost (\$/ha)	Gross income (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
	Rice	Second crop				
Rice alone	2.4	-	167	338	171	2.02
Rice - lentil + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.230	211	372	161	1.76
Rice - lentil + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.409	235	472	237	2.01
Rice - lentil + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.365	218	391	173	1.79
Rice - lentil + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.635	242	546	304	2.25
Rice - linseed + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.235	222	442	220	1.99
Rice - linseed + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.498	242	541	299	2.23
Rice - linseed + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.413	228	506	278	2.21
Rice - linseed + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.664	249	608	359	2.44
Rice - mustard + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.168	203	416	213	2.04
Rice - mustard + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.212	228	438	210	1.91
Rice - mustard + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.199	216	430	214	1.99
Rice - mustard + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.262	230	459	229	1.99

^a Av of 3 crop years. US\$1 = Rs 16.32. ^b S₁ = normal seed rate (kg/ha): linseed 30, lentil 40, mustard 5; S₂ = 50% extra seed than normal (kg/ha): linseed 45, lentil 60, mustard 7.50; F₁ = without fertilizer, F₂ = recommended fertilizer (pulses: 20 kg N + 17.6 kg P/ha) and (oilseeds: 30 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha).

The experiment site had sandy to clay loam soil with pH 8.1, 0.38% organic C, 23.8 kg available P₂O₅, and 267 kg K₂O/ha. Rice variety Madhukar was transplanted the third week of Jul at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Lentil variety PL 406, linseed variety Mukta, and mustard variety Varuna were broadcast in the standing rice crop 8 d before harvest the last week of Nov.

All the dry season crops produced higher grain yields with higher seeding rates and fertilizer (see table). The highest net return was with rice - linseed at higher seeding rate + fertilizer (\$359/ha), followed by rice - lentil at higher seed rate + fertilizer (\$304/ha). Lowest net return was with rice - lentil at normal seeding rate without fertilizer. □

Bullock power use on Tamil Nadu rice farms.

Year	Cost of hired bullock (\$/ha)	Cost of owned bullock (\$/ha)	Total bullock cost (\$/ha)	Total bullock pair use (h/ha)	Total production cost (\$/ha)	Bullock cost: total cost (%)
1971-72	2.67	4.81	7.48	255.29	96.89	7.72
1972-73	(35.70) 2.17	(64.30) 3.51	5.68	283.34	92.36	6.15
1973-74	(38.20) 2.67	(61.80) 4.81	7.48	219.10	72.48	10.32
1974-75	(35.70) 4.41	(64.30) 6.91	11.32	199.77	197.90	5.72
1975-76	(38.96) 3.43	(61.04) 13.29	16.72	224.76	165.71	10.09
1976-77	(20.50) 2.06	(79.50) 17.39	19.45	230.65	166.52	11.68
1977-78	(10.59) 2.99	(89.41) 15.26	18.25	186.64	187.37	9.74
1978-79	(16.38) 3.87	(83.62) 17.97	21.84	231.61	219.28	9.96
1979-80	(17.72) 4.18	(82.28) 23.07	27.25	182.85	241.36	11.29
1980-81	(15.34) 3.05	(84.66) 22.31	25.36	203.80	259.84	9.76
1981-82	(12.02) 6.78 (24.91)	(87.98) 20.44 (75.09)	27.22	223.37	338.98	8.03
1982-83	3.85	32.15	36.00	251.29	422.04	8.53
1983-84	(10.69) 7.71 (28.29)	(89.31) 19.54 (71.71)	27.25	204.35	365.77	7.45

^a Figures in parentheses are percent of total bullock cost/ha.

production costs for hiring bullocks has fallen (from 35-39% earlier to 10-20% in 1984) due to increased use of machinery. □

ENVIRONMENT

Preliminary study on response of rice seedlings to enhanced UV-B radiation

V. P. Coronel, Q. J. Dai, and B. S. Vergara, *Plant Physiology Unit, Agronomy, Plant Physiology, and Agroecology Division, IRRI; and A. Teramura, Department of Botany, University of Maryland, College Park, MD 20742, USA*

We assessed the effect of elevated UV-B radiation on morphological characteristics and physiological processes of rice seedlings. Differences among rice genotypes in growth characteristics in response to enhanced UV-B can provide important information on the mechanisms of and adaptation for UV-B tolerance.

Irrigated rice varieties IR30, IR45, IR64, and IR74 were tested in a randomized block design with three replications. Six pregerminated seeds were sown in 1-liter plastic pots containing 1.7 kg Maahas clay soil (Andaqueptic Haplaquoll). Fertilizer was applied at 0.4 g N, 0.04 g P, and 0.25 g K/kg soil.

Seedlings were raised in the greenhouse for 10 d, thinned to four plants

per pot, and transferred to a phytotron glasshouse for UV-B treatment.

UV-B radiation was supplied by two banks of 12-Q panel UV-B 313 sun-lamps. Lamps were filtered with cellulose acetate for UV-B treatment and with mylar film for control. Lamp height was 40 cm above the top of the plant canopy, as adjusted weekly. Weighted daily UV-B irradiance was about 19 kJ/m² biologically effective UV-B, using the generalized plant response action spectrum normalized at 300 nm.

Plants were irradiated daily for 6 h centered around solar noon for 4 wk. Glasshouse day/night temperature was 27/21°C and relative humidity was 70%.

UV-B treatment significantly decreased plant height, total leaf length of main culm, and total leaf dry weight of main culm (see table). Response varied among the test cultivars. IR74 was the most sensitive, IR64 the least. Cultivar differences were evident in shoot dry weight and total dry weight.

These results indicate that enhanced UV-B irradiation can alter rice plant morphology and (possibly) several physiological processes. The leaves appear to be the organ most sensitive to this environmental stress. The morphological changes in rice, however, do not appear to be as drastic as those reported for other C₃ species. □

Response of 4 rice varieties to 4 wk UV-B radiation at the seedling stage in the phytotron. IRRI, 1989.

Character	IR30	IR45	IR64	IR74
Plant height (cm)	—**	—**	—**	—*
Max root length/plant (cm)	—	+	—	—
Root volume/plant (cm ³)	+	—	—	—**
Tiller number/plant	+	—	+	—**
Leaf area/plant (cm ²)	—	—	—	—**
Leaf dry weight/plant (g)	—	—*	—	—**
Sheath dry weight/plant (g)	—	—	—	—**
Root dry weight/plant (g)	—	—	—	—**
Shoot dry weight/plant (g)	—	—*	—	—**
Dry weight/plant (g)	—	—*	—	—**
Specific leaf weight (mg/cm ²)	—	—	+	+
Relative growth rate (mg/g per d)	—	—*	—	—**
Net assimilation rate (g/m ² per d)	—	—	+	—**
Shoot-to-root ratio	+	—	+	—**
Total leaf length of main culm (cm)	—**	—**	—**	—*
Total leaf area of main culm (cm ²)	—	+	—	—
Total leaf dry weight of main culm (g)	—**	—*	—	—**

+ positive effect of UV-B. — negative effect of UV-B. * significant at 0.05 level. ** significant at 0.01 level.

ANNOUNCEMENT

ICAR celebrates 25 years of rice research

India's Directorate of Rice Research will mark 25 yr of work on rice with an international symposium in November 1990. Rice scientists from all over the world will participate in a three-day program that will include presentation of formal papers and poster sessions.

Four technical sessions are planned: research accomplishments and challenges, genetics and biotechnology, space and communication technology, and futurology.

The Directorate of Rice Research began as the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) in 1965.

For information about the symposium, contact

Dr. E. A. Siddiq, organizing secretary
International Symposium of Rice Research - New Frontiers
Directorate of Rice Research
Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030
India